

TRANSLATION AS A ASPECT OF LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

Currently, modern machine translation programs cannot provide high quality translation of texts of any complexity and, of course, do not claim to be a complete replacement for a human translator. However, machine translation has been successfully applied in three main cases. Firstly, the program is compiled for the translation of narrowly specialized texts, standard in form, with a limited vocabulary and grammar. Secondly, the machine makes it possible to quickly obtain a large volume of low-quality translations, which make it possible to judge the general content of the originals and decide what it is advisable to give the translator in them for more accurate reproduction. Thirdly, an editor is included in the work, who either prepares the text for translation (pre-editing), eliminating or clarifying places difficult for the machine, or editing the already translated text (post-editing), eliminating errors and inaccuracies.

Keywords: translation studies, activity, theory, goal, scientific analysis, linguistics, translation problems, communication, pragma-linguistic

The lack of interest of many linguists in translation problems in the first half of the 20th century was facilitated by the predominance of the ideas of structuralism in linguistic science. In an effort to provide an objective description of the language, to bring linguistics closer to the "exact" sciences, linguists readily accepted Saussure's call to study the language "in and for themselves", confining themselves to the area of "internal linguistics" or otherwise "micro-linguistics". Achieving scientific accuracy and objectivity, linguists have focused their attention on those aspects of the linguistic structure that can be directly observed, measured, counted, demonstrably described and classified: the sound, morphemic and lexical composition of the language, its syntactic structure, syntagmatic and paradigmatic connections of its units, their compatibility, distribution in texts (distribution), frequency of use, etc. As a result, linguistics has made significant progress in the scientific analysis of the structural organization of many languages.

Among the many complex problems that modern linguistics studies an important place is occupied by the study of the linguistic aspects of inter-lingual speech activity which is called "translation" or "translation activity" [3].

Translation is a complex multifaceted phenomenon, some aspects of which can be the subject of research in different sciences. Within the framework of translation studies, psychological, literary, ethnographic and other aspects of translation activity are studied, as well as the history of translation activity in a particular country or countries. Depending on the subject of research, one can single out psychological translation studies (the psychology of translation), literary translation studies (the theory of artistic or literary translation), ethnographic translation studies, historical translation studies, etc. The leading place in modern translation studies belongs to linguistic translation studies (linguistics of translation), which studies translation

as linguistic phenomenon. Separate types of translation studies complement each other, striving for a comprehensive description of translation activities.

The purpose of translation is to acquaint the reader as closely as possible with a text in a foreign language that he does not know. "... to translate means to express correctly and completely by means of one language what has already been expressed earlier by means of another language." [4]. Translation can be carried out, firstly, from one language to another unrelated, related, closely related, secondly, from a literary language to a dialect and vice versa, thirdly, from the language of the ancient period to the modern language.

The reasons for the existence of the translation business: the presence of different languages, different cultures and mentalities. Translation is a way to overcome language and cultural barriers. Language barriers are absolute values cultural barriers are relative, but no less complex barriers to communication. [3].

The theory of translation in its linguistic aspect analyzes, explains and generalizes the facts of translation experience, establishes correspondences and discrepancies between languages. [4]. Based on the general patterns identified by the theory of translation, specific conclusions can be drawn in the future in relation to particular cases.

The "field material" for the study is the texts of the original and the translation, the comparison of which provides objective factual data for subsequent theoretical generalizations. Thus, the study of translation aims, first of all, to describe real translation facts. Having found out the actual ratio of units of two languages that occurs in the process of translation, the theory of translation can then develop recommendations on what methods it is advisable for the translator to use in order to ensure the correct choice of translation option. [1].

The theory of translation explores translation as a special kind of speech activity and analyzes its linguistic mechanism.

According to A. D. Schweitzer, the subject of translation theory is the process of translation in a broad socio-cultural context, taking into account extra-linguistic factors (social, cultural and psychological determinants) that influence it. [5].

The general theory of translation creates a conceptual apparatus for describing translation, reveals its general patterns and invariant features, creates a basis for particular theories of translation, consider the following problems:

- the essence of translation;
- equivalence;
- translatability;
- translation standards;
- pragmatic and semantic problems of translation.

V. N. Komissarov rightly expands the subject of translation theory to the study of the features of different types of linguistic mediation, which, as a rule, were taken out of the scope of the subject of translation theory. Translation and other types of linguistic mediation is the subject of study of the science of translation - translation studies. [1].

The theory of translation is, first of all, a descriptive theoretical discipline that deals with the identification and description of the objective laws of the translation process, which are based on the features of the structure and rules of functioning of the languages involved in this process. In other words, the theory of translation describes not what should be, but what is, what constitutes the nature of the phenomenon under study. At the same time, based on the description of the linguistic mechanism of translation, it is possible to formulate some normative recommendations, principles and rules, methods and techniques of translation, following which the translator can more successfully solve the tasks facing him. In all cases, scientific analysis of observed facts precedes normative prescriptions.

Normative recommendations developed on the basis of translation research can be used both in the practice of translation and in the preparation of future translators. The ability to use such recommendations, modifying them depending on the nature of the translated text and the conditions and tasks of a particular translation act, is an important part of translation skills. Knowledge of regulatory requirements does not imply thoughtless, mechanical implementation of these requirements by the translator. Translation in any case is a creative mental activity, the implementation of which requires the translator to have a whole range of knowledge, skills and abilities, the ability to make the right choice, taking into account the totality of linguistic and extra-linguistic factors. Accounting for such factors occurs largely intuitively, as a result of a creative act, and individual translators, to varying degrees, have the ability to successfully carry out the translation process. A high degree of such skill is called the art of translation.

The phenomenon of linguistic pragmatics is most directly related to the process of linguistic translation of texts from one language to another. "Pragmatics is a field of research in semantics and linguistics which studies the functioning of linguistic signs in speech". In

linguistics, pragmatics has a range of tasks that study the three components of communicative-pragmatic unity. Firstly, these are tasks related to the subject of speech, here the phenomenon or hidden goals of the utterance, speech tactics and types of speech behavior, the attitude of the speaker, the speaker's reference are studied, i.e. assignment of linguistic expressions to objects of reality, etc. Secondly, these are tasks related to the addressee of speech here we study the issues of interpreting speech, the impact of statements on the addressee, types of speech response to the received stimulus, etc. Thirdly, these are tasks related to with the relationship between the participants in communication here the forms of speech treatment, the social and etiquette side of speech, the influence of the situation on the subject and form of communication are studied [6].

Thus, the phenomenon of linguistic pragmatics studies the situation of verbal communication from a different angle than the theory of intercultural communication. The latter usually focuses on the informative side of the phenomenon being studied, namely, what information the active communicant sends, how this information loses in volume or, on the contrary, grows when sent to the passive communicant - the addressee, and how much information reaches the addressee; it is the study of the informative richness of an information source that undergoes various modifications in the process of communication that is one of the main tasks of this theory [7]. Linguistic pragmatics, on the other hand, more accurately reflects the studied linguistic and translation problem of the interaction of the linguistic personalities of the author, translator and reader, since it focuses on the issues of the relationship between the linguistic expression of the message and the situation of verbal communication, in which the active communicant - the author and the passive one, the communicant - the reader enters into verbal and nonverbal communication. Having put forward as a unifying principle the purposeful use of language by communicants in communicative situations and the pragma-linguistic competence of communicants, pragmatic linguistics has covered many problems of linguistics and translation; and therefore the problem of linguistic personalities we are considering finds its solution in the depths of pragma-linguistics. The pragma-linguistic component "subject of speech" is nothing but the linguistic personality of the author, since both of them manifest the active creative side of the phenomenon in an identical way. The pragma-linguistic component "speech addressee" directly correlates with the linguistic personality of the reader, since both of them experience some impact on themselves in terms of receiving information.

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COMPREHENSION OF THE CREATIVITY OF MUKHTAR SHAKHANOV BY PROFESSIONAL FOREIGN READERS

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Abstract

The article deals with the dissemination of the works of Mukhtar Shakhanov in the world thanks to translations into foreign languages and as a result of presentations of his books which were held in many countries. The poetry of Mukhtar Shakhanov is popular in many countries. His literary evenings were held in Turkey, Pakistan, Germany, Switzerland, France, Japan.

Keywords: Kazakh poet, translation, foreign languages, reviews.

During the period of independence, the works of the famous Kazakh poet Mukhtar Shakhanov are actively translated into foreign languages and are widely disseminated in the world community.

Presentations of M. Shakhanov's books were held in many cities of the world. For example, in 1993, his poetry evening took place in the Japanese city of Kobe. In 1999, "The Errors of Civilization" was translated into Turkish and Urdu. The publication of this book in Turkey and Pakistan was accompanied by poetry evenings of the Kazakh poet. In the same year, a presentation of the book "The Errors of Civilization" in German took place in Germany and Switzerland. German literary figures Friedrich Hitzer, E. Pieper and Nobel Prize laureate Hans-Peter Duerr took part in the discussion. In 1999, in France, in Paris, where the headquarters of UNESCO is located, the epic poem "The Errors of Civilization" by M. Shakhanov was presented. Esan Naragi, Friedrich Hitzer, Dudu Dien expressed their opinion about the poem. According to V.Lomeiko, coordinator of the UNESCO international project "For Dialogue between Cultures and Civilizations", the basic principles of interaction based on understanding are expressed in the Kazakh poet's book. Subsequently, with the support of UNESCO, the translation of the poem "The Errors of Civilization" into the languages of the peoples of the world was organized. By the way, the first presentation of this novel with the participation of foreign guests took place in 1997 in Kyrgyzstan. At that time UNESCO Director General Federico Mayor, Turkish President Suleyman Demirel and others arrived in Bishkek. Poetry evenings by M. Shakhanov were also successfully held in Sweden, Scotland and other countries.

It should be noted that the novels "The Errors of Civilization" and "The Cosmo-Formula of Chastening

Memory" were translated into many foreign languages and gained worldwide fame. The positive reviews of professional foreign readers, that is, writers, poets and literary critics, which can be read in these books serve as an important evidence that the works of M. Shakhanov were warmly received by the readers.

The Japanese scholar in Turkic studies, professor Hironori Ito read M. Shakhanov's novel "The Cosmo-Formula of Chastening Memory" with great trepidation and excitement. In his opinion, this work is unique because in historical terms, it covers the deadly struggle between good and evil, suggests the idea of an impending catastrophe of lack of spirituality that can destroy humanity. Hironori Ito believes that "the theme of unpredictable consequences of global computerization and success in creating artificial intelligence, which is brilliantly revealed by M. Shakhanov in "The Errors of Civilization", is further developed in the new novel. The Kazakh poet strives to show the consequences of an easy attitude to the main institution of human society – morality" in historical aspect, using the diversity and poetic plasticity" [1, p. 9]. Summing up, Hironori Ito writes: "M. Shakhanov notes the degradation of the spiritual image of modern leaders. If they read this novel, then, in my opinion, it can to some extent give them a bright idea and change their position. Because only universal morality is able to solve the main problem of the mankind – its peaceful existence and progressive development. Believe me; our society today needs just such a book" [1, p. 10].

M. Shakhanov was highly appreciated by the Pakistani poet Said Ahmad, who believes that the Kazakh poet has made a significant contribution to modern world poetry due to his creations: "I translated the poem "The Errors of Civilization" by M. Shakhanov, which received a great response in the Eurasian space, into